

Name : _____

C1. The games really interested me

C2. In general, I was able to stay focused

C3. I enjoyed playing without getting bored

H1. The games are quite easy

H2. I saw that there were hints/help

YES

NO

H3. I used the help

YES

NO

H4. I used the help when I had difficulties

YES

NO

H5. I used the help just to try it

YES

NO

Name : _____

A1. I think GamesHUB clearly tells me when I've won or lost

A2. I understood how to play easily

A3. I can control the game elements the way I want

I1. I don't see the time passing when I play GamesHUB

I2. I forgot about the teacher and my friends while playing

O. What is my favorite game?

Name : _____

K3. I enjoyed sharing my Album content with my friends

K1. I enjoyed the collection topics

K2. I enjoyed seeing my collection grow little by little

O. What is my favorite collection?

O. What did you like most in GamesHUB? Write or draw your answer